

**DIVIDENDS, TRUST AND WOMEN WHO WAIT: FEMALE SHAREHOLDING
AT BANCO DE ESPAÑA (1875-1921).**

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Abstract:

This research highlights the importance of expanding the scope of finance research to explain the gender gap incorporating history with the shareholders of the Bank of Spain (1875-1921). Using a NARDL (nonlinear autoregressive distributed lag) model, we demonstrate that negative dividend variations decrease the presence of female shareholders in the long term, as well as in their own portfolios. The presence of women with shares was also important to attract new female shareholders. Those results are a relevant contribution to the debate on women's financial decision-making, pointing that women's investor profile favored the perception of present dividends over higher future earnings. Moreover, women tended to view their shares as a long-term investment, as an extension of their familial legacy.

Key words:

women shareholders, dividends, trust, Bank of Spain, finance gap

Highlights:

Understanding historical narratives provide essential tools to reduce gender gap in finance.

The case of Banco de España offered a unique window into the financial behavior of women in the past

Over the long term, women display a marked aversion to losses in dividends.

A higher presence of women among shareholders facilitated other women's access to shares.

1. Introduction

An influential body of literature continues to point to the persistence of more conservative investment traits in women than in men when acquiring financial assets (Jianakoplos and

Bernasek 1998; Haag and Brahm 2025; Halko, Kaustia, and Alanko 2012). And while cultural factors such as formal education and modernization have significantly mitigated the gender gap in financial risk-taking, it continues to exist even in highly developed contexts. Finance historical studies have shown that women's participation in the capital market through the contemporary period was intrinsic part of the modernization (Martínez-Rodríguez and Lopez-Gomez 2025). However, historical statements on women's investments are eminently descriptive, inhibiting the dialogue between finance and history.

This paper aims to explain how dividends and market value explained the behavior of women in a historical context: female shareholders of Banco de España (1875 - 1921) (Bank of Spain, hereafter BE). Methodologically, NARLD models have been chosen. These models include the cumulative effects in the long and short term of both positive and negative shocks in a differentiated way; and allow us to know if positive (negative) shocks in dividends have a positive (negative) effect on the number of female shareholders and if this effect is significant and lasting in time. The same applies to stock price.

Our research responds to different scholarly appeals. First, the paper provides a long-term perspective by showing how women's entry into financial markets. Therefore, we challenge the a-historical view that depicts women as newcomers into financial markets. Second, the paper relates to the literature that primarily suggests that women tend to show a preference for present dividends over future earnings due to their conservative nature as investors. We demonstrate that those ecosystems where women were already investors are more likely to attract more women. The general question of the study asks about the behavior of women investors with respect to dividend and the market price of the shares; also about the time dimension in the holding of assets. The hypotheses to be tested are the following

H1: women shareholders prefer assets that generate stable returns

H2: the seniority of women shareholders favors the incorporation of new women shareholders.

The study therefore focuses on the highly relevant topic of the characteristics of women as investors in financial assets, particularly shares. It also provides a long-term vision

that is of interest for its incorporation into policies that seek to reduce the financial knowledge gap between the sexes.

1.2. The history behind the data

The archival support comes from the annual lists of shareholders of the BE. The database, built with a Python model and monitored by a technical specialist, is composed of 60,338 shareholder records for the years 1875 to 1921. This study only analyzes the holdings of men and women with more than 50 shares: the portfolio required to attend the general shareholders' meeting at the BE headquarter in Madrid. The information on shareholders with less than 50 shares requires manual filing work that we cannot undertake in this research. Men and women account for 91.46% of total shareholders with more than 50 shares for the studied period. Therefore, BE represented a privileged ecosystem to study how men and women financially behave.

Database period is relevant in historical terms. BE had the monopoly to issue currency throughout the country since 1875. The bank was the most relevant corporation on the national scene, even so, debt securities (such as public debt) were the most important financial assets in private hands, with a share fluctuating between 40% and 60% of gross financial assets in the first decades of the 20th century (Blanco, Bauluz, and Martínez-Toledano 2021). During this forty-years, Spain underwent a process of modernization and political stability. Regarding women's rights, there was no (formal) sex discrimination on the ownership and inheritance of movable and immovable property, although the marital leave limited the decision-making for married women. In terms of professional training, there was still a timid presence of qualified women in urban areas (Otero Carvajal and Rodríguez Martín 2022). However, our shareholders are the economic and social elite of the country (Robledo 1988). This does not necessarily mean a climate of greater freedom for women.

1. Methodology

We use Nonlinear Autoregressive Distributed Lag (NARDL) model to examine the asymmetric effects of financial variables on the percentage of female shareholders between 1875-1921. The NARDL approach, proposed by Shin, Yu, and Greenwood-Nimmo (2024), is well-suited for financial time series because it can capture both short- and long-run asymmetries in economic relationships, particularly those arising from investor behavior that may differ when reacting to gains versus losses.

The dependent variable is the percentage of women shareholders each year, already explained the source in the previous section. The core explanatory variables are dividends and stock prices, measure as the percentage of the nominal price for each share (500 pesetas— approximately 1,430 euros in 2025 using the historic standard of living¹) (Ministerio de Trabajo Comercio e Industria 1923). Dividend changes are modeled to capture long-run asymmetries, while stock prices are included to reflect short-run asymmetries. Both series are decomposed into their positive and negative cumulative changes using partial sum processes. Additional covariates include real GDP per capita (1990 Geary-Khamis), which reflects macroeconomic context (Prados de la Escosura 2017; 2024); the average number of shares held per shareholder each year, as a proxy of the ownership concentration; and shareholder seniority, measured as the number of years since an investor first appears in the data (starting at one for all shareholders in 1875).

Table 1. Interval averaged variables. Period: 1875-1921.

	Male Shareholders	Female Shareholders	% Male Shareholders	% Female Shareholders	Number of shares	Seniority female	Dividends	Share Market price	GDPpc
1875-1890	643.1	299.5	64.0	29.4	153.04	3.2	101	316.2	3884.4
1891-1906	802.8	525.7	55.5	36.4	141.1	5.0	109.8	415.4	4145.2
1907-1921	631.5	625.1	44.9	44.5	313.3	3.75	110.2	474.9	4732.0

Source: own elaboration

Figure 1 a)-d) and Table 1 provide a visualization of the joint evolution of shareholders, disaggregated by gender, and the financial variables relevant to the study -share price, dividends and average shareholder age-. The graphs offer indications of long-term co-movements between variables, pointing to a possible structural relationship. The visual evidence suggests that the feminization of shareholder ownership was a phenomenon structurally linked to the evolution of the financial market. To analyze whether women show greater financial integration than men in the results section we turn to a more robust analysis.

Figure 1a)-d). Evolution of the percentage of female shareholders and financial variables. Period: 1875-1921.

¹ Average value as reported by ‘Measuring Worth’ for the year 1918.

<https://www.measuringworth.com/calculators/spaincompare/relativevalue.php> (accessed 11 January 2025).

Source: own elaboration

The model is specified as follows:

$$\Delta(\%FS_y) = \alpha_i + \rho_i \%FS_{t-1} + \theta_i^+ D_{t-1} + \theta_i^- D_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \phi_j \Delta \%FS_{t-j} + \sum_{k=0}^{q-1} (\gamma_k^+ \Delta SMP_{t-k}^+ + \gamma_k^- \Delta SMP_{t-k}^-) + \sum \delta_m Z_{mt} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where $\%FS_t$ is the percentage of female shareholders in BE, D_{t-1}^+ and D_{t-1}^- are the positive and negative cumulative changes in dividends (long-run asymmetry). SMP_t^+ and SMP_t^- are the positive and negative changes in stock prices (short-run asymmetry). Z_{mt} represents control variables. Finally, ε_t is the error term. All variables are tested to be I(0) or I(1) using CIPS test and a maximum of 2 lags are allowed to be detected for both the dependent and exogenous ones to avoid multicollinearity problems.

2. Results

2.1. H1: Women shareholders prefer assets that generate stable returns.

Dividends offer a reliable income stream, especially valuable for small investors, for whom selling shares is less appealing than a stable and sustained income over time (Rydqvist, 2025). Therefore, we include dividends in the long-run equation. Stock price,

on the other hand, has an effect on shareholder composition insofar as shareholders exit and enter by selling their shares in response to share price fluctuations (Shefrin and Statman, 1985; Grinblatt and Han, 2005). To explain the feminization of BE shareholding, we will also use this variable modeled for the short run (Table 2).

Tabla 2. NARDL model for $\Delta(\%FS_t)$. Period: 1875-1921.

$\Delta(\%FS_t)$	Coefficients	p - values
	-0.092**	
$\%FS_{t-1}$	(0.048)	0.023
	-0.037**	
NS_{t-1}	(0.015)	0.013
	1.138***	
$\log(GDPpc)_{t-1}$	(0.374)	0.004
	-0.0007	
SP_{t-1}	(0.0005)	0.207
	0.002	
D_{t-1}^+	(0.004)	0.596
	-0.011**	
D_{t-1}^-	(0.005)	0.034
	-4.157	
$\Delta(\log(GDPpc))_t$	(2.750)	0.138
	0.066*	
$\Delta(NS)_t$	(0.036)	0.078
R^2	0.428	
Symmetry test (F-stat) for dividends	6.26	
Bound test (F-Stat)	4.20	
Jarque-Bera test	0.75 (p-value)	
Breusch-Pagan test	0.69 (p-value)	
Breusch-Godfrey test	0.37 (p-value)	

*Significant at 10%, **significant at 5% ***significant at 1%.

The results of the model estimation with respect to the financial variables show that no short-term effects are detected for the stock price. This indicates that female shareholding is not influenced by short-term factors. However, dividends do influence the shareholding, with negative shocks generating a negative and significant effect and positive shocks having no influence. Figure 2 shows the dynamic cumulative effect of dividends on female participation in the bank, and an asymmetric effect is detected, but

the positive response does not increase the percentage (Y-axis) of women in the long term (X-axis) in the BE. Negative shocks in dividends have a negative effect generating a reduction of female long-term investors in the bank (Figure 2, line negative response).

Figure 2. Cumulative Dynamic multiplier. Dividends on % female shareholders. Period: 1875-1921

2.2. H2: The seniority of women shareholders favors the incorporation of new women shareholders.

The results of H1 do not lead us to consider the possibility of some mechanism by which women could perceive positive shocks more and diffuse the strong aversion to possible losses (Sholevar and Bachmann 2025; Wang and Prokop 2025; Bevelander and Page 2011). This mechanism could be the variable time of holding the shares (seniority). We included in the previous model the seniority variable as a multiplicative of the dividend's variable and, therefore, as a long-term factor. Seniority variable considers the combined effect of dividends and average seniority of women in the long run so that the presence

of other women would persuade potential female investors to invest, increasing the percentage of women in the bank (Table 3).

Table 3. NARDL model for $\Delta(\%FS_t)$ including seniority. Period: 1875-1921

$\Delta(\%FS_t)$	Coefficients	p – values
	-0.177***	
$\%FS_{t-1}$	(0.071)	0.017
	-0.035**	
NS_{t-1}	(0.014)	0.022
	1.495***	
$\log(GDPpc)_{t-1}$	(3.595)	0.002
	-0.001**	
SMP_{t-1}	(0.0006)	0.035
	0.004**	
$(D * Female Seniority)_{t-1}^+$	(0.001)	0.015
	0.0008	
$(D * Female Seniority)_{t-1}^-$	(0.0005)	0.178
	-3.207	
$\Delta(\log(GDPpc))_t$	(2.230)	0.159
	-4.100*	
$\Delta(\log(GDPpc))_{t-1}$	(2.057)	0.055
	0.043*	
$\Delta(NS)_t$	(0.039)	0.277
	0.001***	
$\Delta(D * Female Seniority)_t$	(0.0006)	0.003
	-0.002***	
$\Delta(D * Female Seniority)_{t-1}$	(0.0005)	0.000
R^2		0.578
Symmetry test (F-stat) for dividends*Female Seniority		4.37
Bound test (F-Stat)		7.92
Jarque-Bera test		0.50 (p-value)
Breusch-Pagan test		0.58 (p-value)
Breusch-Godfrey test		0.32 (p-value)

*Significant at 10%, **significant at 5% ***significant at 1%.

In this new estimation we again include stock price as a variable in the short term in an asymmetric way, and no asymmetries are detected. There is a negative and significant relationship between the stock price and the evolution of the percentage of female

shareholders in level, and, in the short term, variations in dividends (combined with female seniority), show differentiated effects with a contemporaneous positive effect. Regarding the results referring to seniority and dividends in the long term, the combined effect of both variables is positive and significant. In contrast, the negative shocks in dividends are not significant in the long run. This effect of the trust network provided by women is a long-term impact.

Figure 3. Cumulative Dynamic multiplier. Dividends and seniority on % female shareholders. Period: 1875-1921

Figure 3 shows the cumulative Dynamic multiplier graph of the interaction between dividends and women's seniority. We see that positive increases in this multiplicative effect generate an increase of women in the bank converging to increases in the percentage of women above those that would occur in the absence of the shock, but not in the case of negative shocks that do not have a significant long-run effect when damped by the seniority effect.

3. Discussion

Our results are consistent with the prospect theory of Kahneman and Tversky (Kahneman and Tversky 1979), meaning that economic agents are more sensitive to losses than to

gains, and therefore behavior with respect to different shocks is not symmetrical. Negative shocks, particularly reductions in dividends, generate long-lasting negative effects on investors' perception and behavior, while positive shocks go unnoticed (Michaely, Thaler, and Womack 1995; Benartzi, Michaely, and Thaler 1997). This result shows that women investors were looking for a stable and profitable long-term investment in the bank. With respect to stock prices, no short-term effects are observed. This suggests that BE women did not use their portfolio for immediate returns. A plausible explanation lies in the culture variable since the function of wealth in the hands of women is to be passed on to the next generation (Hernández Nicolás and Martínez Rodríguez 2019; Hernández-Nicolás and Martínez-Rodríguez 2020). With respect to dividends, women were sensitive to negative shocks and not to positive shocks in the long run.

A second relevant result shows that seniority of women as holders of shares favors new women to join the shareholding. A similar idea has been expressed descriptively for the UK by pointing to the phenomenon of the feminization of shareholding (Rutterford 2021): from a silent minority to becoming the dominant type of shareholder (by sex). The financial literature has shown that networks of trust are key to financial access (Guiso et al., 2004). In historical context, trust networks were especially interesting when it came to women, as social reputation was crucial in well standing society. Current literature claims that women tend to trust other women more and to support each other in different types of activities including economic and financial ones (Bevelander and Page, 2011; Wang and Prokp, 2025; Sholevar et al., 2025). For our historical context, without more information is difficult to support the previous. However, the results suggest that the existence of a network of women who remain in the bank for a long time generates confidence in female investors and has a positive effect in the long run. The presence of women in the BE for long periods of time generates an ecosystem and a network of trust that encourages other women to become shareholders.

4. Conclusions

Historical narratives may contribute to modulate knowledge on gender gap in finance. BE offered a unique window into the financial behavior of women in the past. The behavior of female BE shareholders follows the predictions of finance theory and aligns with previous results in the literature. We detected an asymmetry in the reaction of female investors to different types of shocks. Women were more responsive to losses than men.

In addition, women's seniority as shareholders favors the incorporation of new women shareholders in the long run. Trust networks play an important role in this context and are key to women's access to the financial assets. The results obtained contribute to a better understanding of women's financial dynamics in the past century, provide a solid basis for future studies on financial history and women, and help to understand the financial gap that still exists even in the most developed countries.

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